

A STUDY ON LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF CUSTOMERS TOWARDS VARIOUS TECHNOLOGY USED IN PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The main is to trace the developments and the deployment of the technology in banking sector and to study the level of satisfaction of customers towards various technology used in public sector banks. The main objective of the study is to trace the developments and the deployment of the technology in banking sector and to study the level of satisfaction of customers towards various technology used in public banking. For this purpose a sample of 250 was collected from the respondents and the respondents are those who use banking services in Coimbatore were percentage analysis, chi square and weighted average were used as tools to analyse the data. The conclusion is that the overall the customers are satisfied with the service provided by the banks.

Keywords: Technology, Satisfaction, and Banking

Introduction to the Study:

In recent years, the banking industry around the world has been undergoing a rapid transformation. The deepening of information technology has facilitated better tracking and fulfillment of commitments, multiple delivery channels for online customers and faster resolution of issues. In India too, the wave of deregulation in the early 1990s has created heightened competition and greater risks for banks and financial intermediaries. Today, customers expect highest quality services from banks which, if fulfilled, could result in significantly improved customer satisfaction levels. The Indian banking and financial sector has also welcomed this change. Today, more and more Indian banks are trying to differentiate themselves in a fiercely competitive industry. Not only this helps them align their offerings to the constantly evolving customer needs and developments in technology, it also serves to replace some of traditional bank functions, thereby reducing significant overheads associated with bank branches. Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services exceeds specified satisfaction goals." David J. Reibstein (2010).

The Importance of Customer Satisfaction:

The significance of customer satisfaction is enormous in the business world, it has so many advantages and few are shown below:

Customer Loyalty and Retention:

The major importance of satisfying customers is to make them addictive to their products and services and retain them for their life time. In every industry or market there are numerous competitors or business organizations producing goods and services to succeed. Therefore, business organizations have to ensure that they put their strategy in the right order to satisfy their customers in order to differentiate their products and services. As a result of this, customers will become repetitive to the business organization that satisfies them and prefer staying as long as they are always satisfied (Roger Hallowell, 1996, 27).

Review of Literature:

Vinita Kaura, (2013) The purpose of this paper is to examine the effect of service quality, perceived price and fairness and service convenience on customer satisfaction. It also aims to compare multiple regression models between public and new public sector banks. A cross-sectional research on 445 retail banking customers through a questionnaire is conducted. The population of the study consists of valued retail urban customers of banks in Rajasthan, India, who frequently visit bank premises for transactions, have accounts in at least two banks and have availed of at least one information technology based services. Responses are analysed using regression analyses. Dimensions of service quality are employee behavior, tangibility and information technology. Dimensions of service convenience are decision convenience, access convenience, transaction convenience, benefit convenience and post-benefit convenience. For public sector banks, except tangibility, all antecedents have positive impact on customer satisfaction. For public sector banks except tangibility and benefit

convenience all antecedents have positive impact on customer satisfaction. Significant difference in beta coefficient is found between public and public sector banks regarding employee behavior, decision convenience, access convenience and post-benefit convenience.

Objectives of the Study:

Objectives of the Study In this context, the present research study was undertaken:

- ✓ To investigate the factors that influence the level of satisfaction of online customers (i.e. customers using online or Internet banking services) of selected public sector banks in Coimbatore district; and
- ✓ To assessment of relative significance of these factors on overall satisfaction of these online banking customers in Coimbatore district.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ As the study is based on the perceptions of the customers and employees human bias may creep in.
- ✓ As the sources of secondary data vary descriptions in data reporting exist.
- ✓ As the study is limited with 3 months a deep analysis about the study cannot be made.
- ✓ There may be a bias in collecting the primary data with the customers.

Scope of the Study:

The study is to analyse the customers satisfaction towards recent trends of service provided by the bank.

Methodology of Study:

Collection of Data: The type of research methodology is descriptive and analytical. The data collected for the study includes both primary and secondary data.

Secondary Data: The secondary data was collected from the following:

- ✓ Reserve Bank of India: www.rbiindia.com Bulletin, Statistical Tables Relating to Banks in India, Reports on Trend and Progress of Banking in India.
- ✓ Journals of the ICAI management research, Prajnan Journal of Social and Management Sciences, Journals of Professional Banker, Journal of The Indian Institute of Bankers, Journal of Internet Banking and commerce, Journal of Banking & Finance, Indian Journal of Economics.

Primary Data: The data has been collected through a well structured questionnaire and having discussion with sample respondents.

Study Population and Area: The primary data was collected in Coimbatore district only because it is not feasible to collect the data universally

Sample Size Determination: Selecting an appropriate sample size is a critical aspect in research with particular reference to this study. Since the banking customers and employees are so many, a sample of 250 was considered for the purpose of this study. The convenient sample method has been used for customers of the study.

Tools of Analysis:

A Chi-Square Test: The degree of relationship of the independent demographic variables to the respondent's satisfaction on internal marketing and service quality is measured using percentage analysis and chi square analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	182	72.8
	Female	68	27.2
	Total	250	100.0
Age	Below 18	8	3.2
	18-25	91	36.4
	26-35	75	30.0
	Above 35	76	30.4
	Total	250	100.0
Educational qualification	Below 10 th	9	3.6
	Higher secondary	8	3.2
	UG	140	56.0
	PG	93	37.2
	Total	250	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 72.8% are male and 27.2% are female. It shows that most of the respondents are male in our survey. 3.2% are from the age

group of below 18, 36.4% are from the age group of 18-25, 30% are for the age group of 26-35 and 30.4% are from the age group of above 35. It shows that most of the respondents are from the age group of 18-25. 3.6% are below 10th, 3.2% have completed their higher secondary, 56% have completed their UG, 37.2% have completed their PG. It shows that most of the respondents have completed their UG in our survey.

Factors Related to Level of Satisfaction:

Statements	Scales	Frequency	Percent
Level of satisfaction towards customer friendliness attitude	Satisfied	12	2.4
	Moderate	226	45.2
	Dissatisfied	100	20
	Highly dissatisfied	162	32.4
	Total	500	100
Level of satisfaction towards performance of ATM counters	Satisfied	7	1.4
	Moderate	183	36.7
	Dissatisfied	107	21.5
	Highly dissatisfied	201	40.4
	Total	500	100
Level of satisfaction towards know the customer	Highly satisfied	6	1.2
	Satisfied	51	10.2
	Moderate	220	44
	Dissatisfied	158	31.6
	Highly dissatisfied	65	13
Level of satisfaction towards customer grievance & Redressal procedures	Total	500	100
	Satisfied	17	3.4
	Moderate	250	50
	Dissatisfied	142	28.4
	Highly dissatisfied	91	18.2
Level of satisfaction towards security measures at bank	Total	500	100
	Highly satisfied	5	1
	Satisfied	17	3.4
	Moderate	213	42.6
	Dissatisfied	176	35.2
Level of satisfaction towards online bill payment	Highly dissatisfied	89	17.8
	Total	500	100
	Satisfied	27	5.4
	Moderate	155	31
	Dissatisfied	204	40.8
Level of satisfaction towards accessibility of accounting information	Highly dissatisfied	114	22.8
	Total	500	100
	Satisfied	29	5.8
	Moderate	173	34.6
	Dissatisfied	178	35.6
Level of satisfaction towards visual appeal and physical facilities at bank	Highly dissatisfied	120	24
	Total	500	100
	Satisfied	27	5.4
	Moderate	185	37
	Dissatisfied	182	36.4
Level of satisfaction towards maintaining good relationship with customers	Highly dissatisfied	106	21.2
	Total	500	100
	Highly satisfied	1	0.2
	Satisfied	27	5.4
	Moderate	210	42
Level of satisfaction towards customized communication	Dissatisfied	154	30.8
	Highly dissatisfied	108	21.6
	Total	500	100
	Satisfied	43	8.6
Level of satisfaction towards customized communication	Moderate	186	37.2
	Dissatisfied	164	32.8
	Highly dissatisfied	107	21.4
	Total	500	100

	Total	500	100
Level of satisfaction towards easy online application for all accounts	Satisfied	31	6.2
	Moderate	189	37.8
	Dissatisfied	132	26.4
	Highly dissatisfied	148	29.6
	Total	500	100
Level of satisfaction towards knowledge of internet banking in employees	Satisfied	41	8.2
	Moderate	181	36.2
	Dissatisfied	107	21.4
	Highly dissatisfied	171	34.2
	Total	500	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the percentage analysis for the factors related to level of satisfaction towards CRM practices. While analyzing about satisfaction towards customer friendliness attitude 2.4% are satisfied, 45.2% are moderately satisfied, 20% are dissatisfied and 32.4% are highly dissatisfied towards customer friendliness attitude. 1.4% are satisfied, 36.7% are moderately satisfied, 21.5% are dissatisfied and 40.4% are highly dissatisfied towards performance of ATM counters, 1.2% are highly satisfied, 10.2 are satisfied, 44%moderately satisfied, 31.6% are dissatisfied and 13% are highly dissatisfied towards knowing their customers. 3.4 are satisfied, 50%moderately satisfied, 28.4% are dissatisfied and 18.2% are highly dissatisfied towards customer grievance & Redressal procedures. 1% are highly satisfied, 3.4 are satisfied, 42.6%moderately satisfied, 35.2% are dissatisfied and 17.8% are highly dissatisfied towards security measures at bank. 5.4 are satisfied, 31%moderately satisfied, 40.8% are dissatisfied and 22.8% are highly dissatisfied towards online bill payment. 5.8% are satisfied, 34.6%moderately satisfied, 35.6% are dissatisfied and 24% are highly dissatisfied towards accessibility of accounting information.

5.4% are satisfied, 37%moderately satisfied, 36.4% are dissatisfied and 21.2% are highly dissatisfied towards visual appeal and physical facilities at bank.0.2% are highly satisfied, 5.4% are satisfied, 42%moderately satisfied, 30.8% are dissatisfied and 21.6% are highly dissatisfied towards maintaining good relationship with customers.8.6% are satisfied, 37.2%moderately satisfied, 32.8% are dissatisfied and 21.4% are highly dissatisfied towards customized communication.6.2% are satisfied, 37.8%moderately satisfied, 26.4% are dissatisfied and 29.6% are highly dissatisfied towards easy online application for all accounts. 8.2% are satisfied, 36.2%moderately satisfied, 21.4% are dissatisfied and 34.4% are highly dissatisfied towards knowledge of internet banking in employees.

Chi-Square Analysis:

Level of Satisfaction Towards Banking Services Vs Age:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction towards banking services and age of the respondents

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.726E2 ^a	30	.000

Interpretation:

The above tables shows about the relationship between level of satisfaction towards banking services and age were there is a relationship between these two factors as the level of significance is at 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05.

Findings:

Maximum (45.2%) are moderately satisfied towards customer friendliness attitude, most (40.4%) are highly dissatisfied towards performance of ATM counters, most (44%) of the respondents are moderately satisfied towards knowing the customer, Majority (50%) are moderately satisfied towards customer grievance & Redressal procedures, maximum (42.6%) are moderately satisfied towards security measures at bank, maximum (40.8%) are moderately satisfied towards online bill payment, most (35.6%) are dissatisfied towards accessibility of accounting information, most (37%) are moderately satisfied towards visual appeal and physical facilities at bank, maximum (42%) are moderately satisfied towards maintaining good relationship with customers, maximum (37.2%) are satisfied towards customized communication, most (37.78%) are moderately satisfied towards easy online application for all accounts, most (36.2%) are moderately satisfied towards knowledge of internet banking in employees.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The communication skills of the employees can be developed by providing training programs to them.
- ✓ More employees can be employed in call centers so that the respondents will be satisfied for the respondents will be satisfied for the quick response given by them in future period of time.
- ✓ The service quality of the banks can be improved in all levels and also different types of service

provided by the banks to their customers.

- ✓ To improve productivity per employee, Public Sector Banks have to either improve deposit and advances rate of the branches or to decrease the number of employee by introducing VRS scheme again.
- ✓ The banks should adopt more aggressive marketing strategies in line with the new public sector banks to add to the business volumes both in terms of deposits as well as advances.
- ✓ The major asset of the banks being their human resources, they should be redeployed matching their skill sets and providing on the job training wherever necessary in order to derive optimum level of efficiency and productivity. Apparently there is a mismatch in the deployment of resources, which resulted in lower productivity.
- ✓ With numerous technological features coming into day to day banking resulting in diminishing reliance on men than the machines, the excess staff should be used for marketing bank's products thereby increasing volumes in terms of credit as well as deposits.

Conclusion:

India's banking system broadly consists of "non – schedules banks" and scheduled banks". Further, Scheduled banks consist of "scheduled commercial banks: and "scheduled cooperative banks". The main objective of the study is to study the level of satisfaction of customers towards various technology used in public sector banks. For this purpose a sample of 250 was collected from the respondents and the respondents are those who use banking services in Coimbatore were percentage analysis, and chi square were used as tools to analyse the data. The conclusion is that the overall the customers are satisfied with the service provided by the banks.

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